

Complex Compounds of Iridium. Part I.

Compounds with Organic Sulphides.

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Iridium and platinum, placed as they are in the same group of transitional elements in the periodic table, show a remarkable similarity in their inorganic compounds as well as a gradation of properties thereto. Though the methods of preparations are different, they give the same type of chlorides, *e.g.*, iridium monochloride, iridium dichloride, iridium trichloride, iridium tetrachloride and platinum mono-, di-, tri-, and tetrachlorides. Of these iridium mono- and dichlorides are unstable, whereas in the case of platinum, the mono- and the trichlorides are not stable; as to the formation of complexes with alkali chlorides, iridium tri- and tetrachlorides unite to form M_3IrCl_6 and M_2IrCl_6 respectively whereas platinum di- and tetrachlorides yield M_2PtCl_4 and M_2PtCl_6 .

For some years past, Ray and his co-workers, in a series of papers have studied the action of alkyl mono- and disulphides on chloroplatinic acid and potassium chloroplatinate with interesting results. (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **125**, 133; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 178; *ibid.*, 1926, **3**, 338; *ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 467; *ibid.*, 1928, **5**, 139; *Z. anorg. chem.*, 1929, **178**, 329; *ibid.*, 1930, **187**, 33; *ibid.*, 1931, **198**, 53; *ibid.*, 1932, **203**, 401.) The constitution of some of the compounds they obtained could be represented on the basis of Werner's theory while those of others did not come within its purview but the authors proved beyond doubt that the latter are of complex nature and their constitution should be represented as such. A more recent paper by Angell, Drew and Wardlaw (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p. 349) has established that the isomerism found in co-ordinate compounds of platinum is of a structural and not of a spatial nature. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to explore the above possibilities in the iridium compounds of organic sulphides and to examine how far they resemble the corresponding platinum compounds.

In this paper an account of the reaction of iridium tetrachloride with methyl sulphide, ethyl sulphide and diethyl disulphide has been described. The following compounds have been obtained:

- (1) $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ (4) $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$
 (2) $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$... (6) $(\text{IrCl}_2)_2 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$
 (3) $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ (5) $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Et}_2\text{S}$

In the case of platinum, no compounds of the type (1) or (4) were obtained but compounds of the type (2), (3) and (5), *e.g.*, $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ have been isolated. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, easily breaking up into $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, was proved to be a molecular compound but the other one $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ resisted every attempt to break it up and was regarded

as an independent entity, being represented as $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{Cl} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Pt} \\ \diagup \\ \text{Cl} \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \text{Bz}_2\text{S} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Bz}_2\text{S} \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}$

from its various reactions. The compound (2) is almost insoluble in all ionising solvents, and as it could not be split up into $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{IrCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, it is better to represent it as a molecular compound $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$. The compounds (1) and (4) can be represented thus

the co-ordination number of iridium being six. They are non-electrolytes, as is evident from the conductivity measurement in acetone (*vide* experimental). Such trivalent platinum compounds are totally non-existent.

Compounds (3) and (5) behave rather in a different manner from the corresponding platinum analogue $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$, which when recrystallised from hot alcohol breaks up into $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$. But in the present case, the compounds are very stable and from the methods of their preparations, it appears quite unlikely that their constitutions are similar to those of the corresponding platinum compounds. The compound (5) although sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone, separates in well defined crystals from boiling alcohol, the m.p. remaining the same even after two consecutive crystallisations.

The mode of reaction is the same as in the platinum series.

Irididium tetrachloride in presence of sulphides gradually loses chlorine, the reduction being more vigorous when heated in presence of alcohol.

As to the constitution of $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$, it can only be stated here that the disulphides are stronger reducing agents than the monosulphides and so in this case the reduction of iridium tetrachloride has proceeded a step further to iridium dichloride and it might be represented as $2(\text{IrCl}_2) \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$.

Had it been possible to arrest the above reactions stage by stage, the course and the mode of the formation of the different products could be further elucidated. The compounds (1) and (2) were the results of carrying on the reactions entirely in cold but when the same reaction was conducted on water-bath, (2) could not be isolated from the filtrate; only (3) was obtained and also an inseparable mixture containing a lower percentage of iridium (43.5) than both (2) and (3) but much higher than that of (1).

Iridium was estimated by slowly igniting the compound in a rose crucible and then reducing by hydrogen till the weight is constant and finally cooling the crucible in a current of carbon dioxide. This presented some difficulties as the compounds, (prepared from IrCl_4 supplied by Messrs. Schering-Kahlbaum) when reduced, sublimed and condensed in a very thin film on the lid and on the leading pipe. This film is insoluble in aqua regia, which, therefore, precludes the presence of rethenium and osmium but its weight is so small that it is not appreciable even after 6 or 7 operations.

The replacements of sulphides of these compounds by amines and ammonia are in progress and will be the subject of the next communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.—To iridium tetrachloride (6g.),

di-methyl-sulphide (5g.) in alcohol (about 20 c.c.) was added and kept in closed conical flask with occasional shaking. The chloride dissolved completely in about 8 hours. After 24 hours the solution was heated under reflux on a water bath. After an hour a precipitate, yellow in colour, began to separate. The refluxing was stopped after 4 hours. The yellow precipitate was mixed up with a tarry mass which also came out during the above process. The entire mass was filtered hot and the filtrate concentrated in a vacuum desiccator. The residue was repeatedly extracted with hot alcohol and these extracts on concentration yielded yellow crystals, m.p. 228-230°, which on recrystallisation from warm alcohol melted at 238-39° (I); the insoluble residue—a grey coloured mass, was rather too small to be further purified for analysis. The main filtrate which was concentrated as indicated above, turned to a semisolid mass. It was then filtered under a strong suction and a crystalline substance was left behind. This was washed with a little alcohol and ether and finally recrystallised from warm alcohol (II) m.p. 238-39° with evolution of Me_2S but it did not break up into the metallic state as was also the case with the compound I. It is soluble in acetone and sparingly so in cold alcohol and benzene etc. Both products (I and II) were analysed and found to have the same composition. (Found: Ir, 40.39; Cl, 21.83; C, 14.30; S, 20.68. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ requires Ir, 39.75; Cl, 21.93; C, 14.83; S, 19.79 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.—The filtrate from the above was concentrated in vacuum to a tarry solid mass to which hot alcohol was added. Most of the tarry matter dissolved and a yellow substance was left behind. This was separated and the filtrate again evaporated in a vacuum, dissolved in hot alcohol. This process was repeated until the evaporated filtrate was completely soluble in alcohol without leaving any residue. The first crop and the next successive portions were found to be mixtures. The filtrate was then evaporated on water bath to dryness and the mass digested with boiling alcohol when a yellow substance separated out. This was refluxed with acetone on water-bath and filtered. The process was repeated till the acetone was almost colourless. It was finally washed with chloroform and ether—dried and analysed. It has got no m.p. and is very sparingly soluble in acetone, alcohol and other organic solvents. (Found: Ir, 47.90; Cl, 22.19; C, 11.28. $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ requires Ir, 47.59; Cl, 21.83; C, 11.83 per cent.).

Second method of preparation.—When $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ was refluxed with alcohol and the solution together with traces of insoluble matter held in suspension, evaporated to dryness on water-bath and the process repeated 6–7 times, almost the whole of the substance became sparingly soluble in boiling alcohol and acetone. The undissolved portion was then collected, washed several times with hot alcohol and acetone and finally with ether and dried. It has no m.p. but gradually decomposes when heated above 200° . (Found: Ir, 47.41; Cl, 22.16 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.—Methyl sulphide (3.3g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was added to iridium tetrachloride (4g.) and the vessel kept closed. After 2 days a dirty precipitate began to separate out and this increased gradually up to the 4th day. To ensure complete reaction it was filtered off (after 7 days), the precipitate being digested with hot alcohol and acetone till the filtrate was almost colourless. The insoluble portion was too small to be further purified for analysis and was stored for investigation in future. The wash alcohol, on evaporation on water-bath to dryness, yielded a yellow substance, which on analysis (after purification) was found to be identical with the compound $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Me}_2\text{S}$. Three crops of a yellow substance were successively (I, II & III) obtained when the main filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum and subsequently digested with alcohol and the process thus repeated thrice. The alcoholic filtrate was next evaporated on water-bath to dryness and kept over it until the resulting black tarry mass became dull grey. This was lixiviated with hot alcohol when a yellow residue was left. It was washed with hot chloroform and alcohol to remove the last traces of the tarry matter. The filtrate obtained in this stage was too small for further investigation. The crops I and II were found to be impure but III and also the yellow precipitate obtained by evaporation on water-bath were found to be identical in composition. They have no sharp m.p. but decompose slowly above 200° . (Found: Ir, 45.36, 45.08; Cl, 24.92, 24.63; S, 15.59. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$ requires Ir, 45.57; Cl, 25.14; S 15.13 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.— IrCl_4 (8 g.) and Et_2S (8 c.c.) in 50 c.c. alcohol were mixed together and refluxed for three hours. The mixture was then subjected to filtration when a very small amount of black residue remained behind. The filtrate on concentration in vacuum yielded a crystalline mass; it was collected and recrystallised from hot benzene in

which a very small portion—greyish white in colour—remained insoluble. It is soluble freely in benzene, chloroform and acetone and moderately so in alcohol and insoluble in water, m.p. 131°. (Found: Ir, 33·58; Cl, 19·01; S, 17·14; C, 26·02. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires Ir, 33·86; Cl, 18·68; S, 16·86; C, 25·28 per cent). The filtrate from the above on further concentration yielded a crop m.p. 194° (not sharp) which was too small for analysis. Finally the remaining tarry filtrate was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and digested with alcohol, when a lemon yellow substance remained undissolved. This was collected, washed with benzene and chloroform in which it is sparingly soluble. The substance was dried and analysed, m.p. 207°. (Found: Ir, 42·06; Cl, 18·62; C, 19·23; S, 10·83. $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$, requires Ir, 41·82; Cl, 19·23; C, 20·80; S, 13·86 per cent). The above compound was also obtained when $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ in alcohol, was refluxed for 30-35 hours; about 60% of the substance changed to $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$. It was then washed several times with hot benzene and acetone. (Found: Ir, 42·33 per cent.).

The Molar Conductivity of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ at Different Concentrations in Acetone at 25·5°.

TABLE I.

Molar conc.	0·008738	0·004360	0·002184	0·001092
Molar conductivity.	2·75	2·95	3·72	4·46

TABLE II.

Molar conc.	0·01281	0·00640	0·00320	0·00160
Molar conductivity.	2·59	2·77	3·02	3·36

Preparation of $(\text{IrCl}_2)_2 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$.— IrCl_4 (2g.) in alcohol and Et_2S_2 (2g.) were mixed together and heated on water-bath under reflux. The chloride gradually dissolved and a deep red almost black liquid resulted. This was then evaporated on a water-bath with constant stirring till there was no evolution of hydrochloric acid. The solid tarry matter, thus obtained, was then triturated with alcohol when a yellow solid separated and a

deep red solution was left behind. The yellow substance was several times extracted with boiling alcohol when it almost completely dissolved and an orange yellow crystalline mass was obtained from the filtrate on cooling. The residue was small and could not be further purified. The main mother liquor (the above deep red solution) on concentration (1st and 2nd crop) in vacuum yielded an orange coloured crystalline substance identical with the preceding one and the succeeding crops gave anomalous analytical results. The substances were further purified by dissolving them in chloroform and precipitating with ether. It does not melt but gradually decomposes into the metallic state above 200°. (Found: Ir, 42.74; Cl, 15.06, 14.79; S, 21.66, 21.8. $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$ requires Ir, 43.17; Cl, 15.83; S, 21.47 per cent.).

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